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USING FILM IN ENGINEERING ETHICS EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In our engineering ethics teaching, we use films to illustrate and exemplify the ethical implications of engineering. While engineering ethics education can sometimes be seen as a chore or a box to be ticked, we argue that the use of film can contribute to a number of learning outcomes in engineering ethics education such as stimulating moral imagination and eliciting a sense of responsibility. In this paper, we argue that film could make the integration of ethics more meaningful to students by revealing and addressing their emotions, and by bringing fun and excitement into the classroom. We discuss different ways in which film could be used, and their benefits and drawbacks. Educators could: 1) micro-insert references to film, and illustrate or have students discuss ethical concepts using episodes from films. 2) encourage students to watch a film (chosen by the student) and have them analyse it from an ethical perspective. 3) collectively watch a film followed by discussion or activity. 4) encourage students to script and produce a narrative, which could be filmed or performed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In our engineering ethics teaching, we use films like *Black Mirror*, *Star Wars*, and *Gattaca* to illustrate the ethical implications of engineering. While engineering ethics education can sometimes be seen as a chore or a box to be ticked (e.g. [3]), we argue that the use of film can be an interesting and exciting way to contribute to a number of learning outcomes in engineering ethics education such as stimulating moral imagination and eliciting a sense of responsibility. In a foundational paper in engineering ethics education, Harris et al. [4] produce a set of learning outcomes, namely, that it should:

- stimulate the ethical imagination of students,
- help students recognize ethical issues,
- help students analyze key ethical concepts and principles,
- help students deal with ambiguity,
- encourage students to take ethics seriously,
- increase student sensitivity to ethical issues,
- increase student knowledge of relevant standards,
- improve ethical judgment,
- increase ethical will-power.

Because film evokes emotions, imagination, sensibilities, and a connection to the personal, we believe that it can play a crucial role in engineering ethics education, not least because such education will not have an impact if it only becomes an exercise in moral reasoning without any connection to one's self [9, 10].

Given this, we find it remarkable that there is not an ongoing discussion about the use of film within engineering ethics education research. A search using the keywords “engineering ethics” AND “film” on Scopus returned only three papers that were returned, namely Berne [1] about the use of *The Matrix* in engineering ethics teaching, one paper by Riley [12] on a feminist critique of the educational film *Henry's Daughters*, and a short piece about the educational film *Incident at Morales* [13]. While not explicitly linked to engineering, Teays [11] presents an interesting how-to guide which suggests five strategies for using film in ethics classes. The paper includes a significant number of examples and exercises that the ethics instructor can be inspired by. However, it lacks explicit links to engineering education and learning outcomes.

Our paper is therefore aimed at developing this conversation, which can include reasons why film can be used in engineering ethics education, how it can promote different learning outcomes, and the advantages and disadvantages of using film in these contexts. We want to stress that we do not see film as *the* way to teach engineering ethics, but as *one* way: an educational method that can complement other more well-trodden routes, such as discussions about codes of conduct, case studies, and ethical tools [5]. Another clarification is that by describing film, we mainly mean those that are fictional, but could also include documentary films or

films that are produced for the specific purpose of engineering ethics education. In this short paper we present four different ways in which film can be used, and illustrate each use with examples from our own teaching practice, which is followed by a concluding discussion.

2 USING FILM

There are several options available for educators wishing to use film in engineering ethics education, to some extent inspired by different ways of using drama in engineering ethics education [2]:

2.1 Micro-insertions: use references to film, and illustrate or have students discuss ethical concepts using episodes from films

Here, film is micro-inserted into an engineering ethics curriculum. For example, the story of the software engineer Morris in the TV series *24* and his ethical conundrum when he is kidnapped on his way to work and forced by terrorists to arm a dirty bomb to be detonated in the middle of a large US city can be a dramatic opening to a textbook [8] or course. Similarly, an instructor could lecture about this little episode in class, perhaps discussing it in terms of the concept of free will and coercion - how much responsibility does Morris really have for the consequences if he is tortured into arming the bomb?

Another somewhat more substantial, but still time-efficient exercise, is to use the case of Galen Erso found in *Rogue One*. After watching a clip of Luke Skywalker blowing up the Death Star in *Star Wars IV: A New Hope*, we turn the perspective over to the chief engineer of the Death Star, namely Galen Erso. He is forced to work for the Empire, so designs the Death Star with a flaw and leaks the drawings to the rebels so they can destroy it. The students can then be asked to analyse Galen Erso's action by using the ten principles in the Swedish honour code for engineers: which principles were followed and which were breached? This is a way to have students familiarize themselves with the honour code in an engaging way.

2.2 Encourage students to watch a film of their choice and have them analyse it from an ethical perspective

In this example, students could choose a film from a list of options, perhaps all centred around one topic. For instance, in the category of Artificial Intelligence (A.I.), films include *Her*, *2001: A Space Odyssey*, *Ex Machina*, and *Chappie*. Students could watch the chosen film as individuals or in groups, and analyse the conflicts and character choices according to ethical theories, principles or motivations. Each student or group could give a presentation to the rest of the class about how they found ethics to underpin the issues raised by the film, or write reflections about their personal reactions to the possibilities and potential perils of A.I. Additionally, technical and historical aspects can be brought into a class discussion: students could analyse the accuracy of the portrayal of A.I. technology and consider the

perspectives of filmmakers and the public on their reactions to A.I. at different points in time.

In the course “Nature and Human Values” (NHV) at the Colorado School of Mines, instructors regularly use film to complement teaching about the ethics of different emerging technologies. NHV has had a structure that combines a large lecture with smaller seminar sections, and film has been used in both learning formats. For instance, in the unit about nuclear technology, excerpts of the documentary *The Day After Trinity* were shown to the large lecture section to present the reflections of the Los Alamos nuclear scientists and engineers on their efforts 40 years previously to build the atomic bomb. These film excerpts fed into ethical concepts like dual use and whistleblowing. In smaller seminar groups, students have watched episodes of *Star Trek* or excerpts from *Gattaca* to spur discussion about issues surrounding cognitive robotics, autonomy, and moral agency. These discussions enable students to increase awareness about ethical implications of technologies on people, culture, and policy [7].

2.3 Collectively experience a film followed by discussion or activity

Another possibility is to collectively watch a film and have a discussion about it afterwards. Positive effects include that all students experience the film concurrently, so emotional responses might be enhanced by the reactions of others. It is also a way to have all students watch the same film, rather than different ones, which means that they can all relate to the film and have an informed discussion with potentially diverging interpretations of what they saw.

At Uppsala University, we organized a voluntary meet-up with students in financial mathematics, to discuss the ethics of the finance industry. To do this we screened the film *Margin Call*, with an explicit encouragement that students should discuss the film afterwards, fueled by abundant servings of popcorn and non-alcoholic beverages, which was easily handled as the main teacher of the course had some funding. It was a bit complicated to get the rights from the Swedish distributor to show the film. Once approved, the film screening all took place in the teachers’ room at the Department of Information Technology, a spacious room with sofas, chairs, tables, and ideal for relaxed, creative discussions. After the screening, the student sat down in groups of five, and discussed different questions, for example: What were the ethical dimensions of the film? How does the finance industry work, and what subjectivities does it shape? Two teachers were walking around in the room discussing with the different groups. Groups argued intensely about issues including wage differentials and salary gaps.

2.4 Encourage students to script and produce a narrative, which could be filmed or performed

In this activity, students are charged with writing, directing, and producing a film related to a topic on engineering ethics. The film’s focus could range from professional situations such as those covered by the National Institute for

Engineering Ethics (students could even be asked to update or modernise the existing films) to covering ethical concerns like privacy, diversity, or autonomy, and they could be either documentary or fictional. For instance, in a class about “Water and the West” which addressed issues of sustainability and justice around water consumption in Colorado, some Mines honors students created a film in conjunction with their efforts to conserve water during the annual “World Water Day” initiative. Another option is for students to re-write the endings to existing films in order to demonstrate what would have happened if a character had made a different choice, or to explore a character’s perspective that wasn’t shown in the original. This example may be the most time-consuming and resource-intensive option, but it can also help students to practice relevant skills and meet engineering learning outcomes in other areas, such as teamwork, project management, and communication.

3 CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

As we have seen, using film in engineering ethics education has the potential to bring many benefits to students ranging from meeting learning outcomes to improving attitude toward what can sometimes seem to be dry or uninteresting topics. Film also provides the opportunity for instructors to incorporate other high-impact educational practices such as writing, collaboration, and even research into both technical and ethics courses [6]. However, some challenges and limitations do need to be addressed. Of course, some of these activities can be time-consuming, especially if they involve watching films together or scripting and producing a film or performance. Additionally, films might reinforce or amplify existing stereotypes about engineers, technologies, or cultures in terms of how characters or situations are represented and portrayed. Left un-critiqued, these could actually be detrimental to ethics education. Finally, there is still a perspective that film study is not “serious” or intellectually challenging, perhaps contingent on the hidden curriculum in engineering education [14], and instructors and students alike may be criticized for engaging with it as a method of learning.

To sum up, film can be an impactful addition to a program of engineering ethics learning. It is a way for students to consider the relationship of emotion to morality, to practice their ability to recognize ethical dilemmas, to analyse the perspectives of different stakeholders and consequences of different decisions, and to apply ethical reasoning to various scenarios. In many respects, it is a place to “play,” trialing ethical habits of mind in a safe-to-fail environment. Used in conjunction with other methods of teaching engineering ethics, film has the potential to make the integration of ethics more meaningful to engineering students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Berne, R.W. 2001. Reaching and teaching through "The Matrix"; robosapiens, transhumanism, and the formidable in engineering ethics, ASEE Annual Conference Proceedings, pp. 8343-8350.
- [2] Birch, P. & Lennerfors, T.T. 2020. Teaching Ethics with Drama, Frontiers in Education 2020 proceedings: <https://aic-atlas.s3.eu-north-1.amazonaws.com/projects/e7299991-eb2b-4764-a849-4909e01fb07d/documents/R6YNrATTkkEmWgJyP3JIECFYUHoe53Lr7sWfXvog.pdf>
- [3] Bowles, C. 2018. Future Ethics, Hove: NowNext Press.
- [4] Harris, C. E. Jr, M. Davis, M. S. Pritchard, and M. J. Rabins. 1996. "Engineering ethics: what? why? how? and when?" Journal of Engineering Education, vol. 85, no. 2, pp. 93–96
- [5] Hess, J.L. & Fore, G. 2018. A Systematic Literature Review of US Engineering Ethics Interventions, Science & Engineering Ethics (2018) 24:551–583.
- [6] Hitt, S.J. et al. "Nature and human values course." (2016), in National Academy of Engineering, *Infusing Ethics into the Development of Engineers: Exemplary Education Activities and Programs*. Washington: National Academies Press, p. 34.
- [7] Hitt, S.J., C.E.P. Holles, and T. Lefton. 2020. "Integrating ethics in engineering education through multidisciplinary synthesis, collaboration, and reflective portfolios." Advances in Engineering Education (2020) pp. 1-11. <https://advances.asee.org/integrating-ethics-in-engineering-education-through-multidisciplinary-synthesis-collaboration-and-reflective-portfolios/>
- [8] Lennerfors, T.T. 2019. Ethics in Engineering, Lund: Studentlitteratur.
- [9] Lennerfors, T., Laaksoharju, M., Davies, M., Birch, P. and Fors, P. A pragmatic approach to teaching ethics to engineers and computer scientists, Frontiers in Education 2020 proceedings: <https://aic-atlas.s3.eu-north-1.amazonaws.com/projects/e7299991-eb2b-4764-a849-4909e01fb07d/documents/kQrLJCWHqt9Q1jzww749jPt2wLNdAL1TWgn9rGS.pdf>
- [10] B. Newberry, "The dilemma of ethics in engineering education," Science and Engineering Ethics, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 343–351, 2004
- [11] Teays, W. 2017. Show Me a Class That's Got a Good Movie, Show Me: Teaching Ethics through Film, Teaching Ethics 17:1 (Spring 2017).
- [12] Riley, D. 2013. Hidden in Plain View: Feminists Doing Engineering Ethics, Engineers Doing Feminist Ethics, Science and Engineering Ethics 19(1), pp. 189-206.
- [13] Stephan, K.D. 2007. Incident at Morales (DVD and VHS), IEEE Technology and Society Magazine 26(4), pp. 6-7.
- [14] Tormey, R., LeDuc, I., Isaac, S., Hardebolle, C., & Cardia, I. V. (2015). The formal and hidden curricula of ethics in engineering education. Paper presented at the 43rd Annual SEFI Conference, Orléans, France.